

Product Approval Committee (PAC) – Membership, Charter, and Roles & Responsibilities

Charter: PAC governs Brooks' portfolio of new footwear product development projects

Roles and Responsibilities:

- Meets at pre-defined times to review entire seasonal lines from a business perspective
 - Concept Brief Approval, Concept Debut, Line Review, Freeze, Production Readiness
- Makes a clear decision on each product in the line
 - "Go" if all business objectives can be met and adequate risk management plans are in place
 - "Redirect" if project gaps can be remedied with confidence—establish a time to confirm that gaps have been closed
 - "No-Go" if project gaps cannot be remedied—project is cancelled outright or deferred to a future line
- Resolves cross-functional conflicts and provides strategic direction to project teams to achieve overall line goals (revenue, margins, brand positioning, etc.)
- Decides as a team and communicates with one voice to the organization

Meeting Interviews with 2 senior executives of Brooks Sports USA
(average interview length 120 min)

Meeting Interviews with 4 junior executives of Brooks Sports USA
(average interview length 90 min)